

Privacy Preservation in Textual Data: A Systematic Mapping Study on Differential Privacy and Semantic Similarity

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Selection Criteria - Inclusion Criteria (IC) Studies were included if they meet the criteria in Table 1.

Table 1. Inclusion Criteria (IC)

Class	IC	Criteria
Topical relevance	IC-1	Focus on semantic text similarity , rarity-aware analysis , and/or privacy-preserving techniques in the context of textual data analysis .
	IC-2	Involve AI models , especially large language models (LLMs) or agent-based approaches applied to textual data.
Publication type and quality	IC-3	Peer-reviewed journal articles , conference proceedings , or preprints with clear methodological descriptions.
	IC-4	Studies published between 2010 and 2025 in English or Brazilian Portuguese.
Application domain	IC-5	Research conducted in relevant contexts , such as legal text mining , social media analysis , compliance , or privacy-sensitive NLP .
Technical depth	IC-6	Must describe at least one implemented or theoretically grounded method for semantic similarity , rarity detection , or privacy protection .